

1 **Current Trends in Rapid Electroanalytical Screening of Date and Rape Drugs in** 2 **Beverages**

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10 sensors.

11 **Abstract**

12 This review covers the current state of the art about electroanalytical studies focused on
13 drugs used to facilitate sexual assaults. The chemicals that are members of this family and
14 the main target of this review paper are benzodiazepines as a family of molecules,
15 ketamine, gamma-hydroxybutyric acid, fentanyl, and some of the drugs categorized as
16 new psychoactive substances (NPS). Most of the research in this area has been published
17 within the last 10 years. Given the need for on-the-spot date rape drugs detection, we have
18 emphasized sensing scenarios that have been developed and validated using real samples,
19 soft and hard drinks. In the background, we also discuss some of the works focused on
20 body fluids, which could be also applied to the soft and hard drinks analysis. Following a
21 critical discussion of the current state of the art, we present a section outlining future
22 directions along with the highlighted existing knowledge gap.

23 **1. Introduction**

24 Date rape drugs (DRD) are a large family of chemical substances that have sedative
25 properties. These molecules can be classified into a few subgroups, this is
26 benzodiazepines (BDZ, e.g. midazolam, temazepam, diazepam, flunitrazepam), ketamine,
27 gamma-hydroxybutyric acid (GHB) , fentanyl, and other less popular psychotropic
28 molecules also including emerging recreational drugs. The statistical analysis of drug-
29 facilitated crimes (DFC) is difficult to assess as victims frequently experience amnesia, or
30 choose not to testify, often out of fear of victim blaming. Even though this issue is very

31 complex, the report of the European Monitoring Centre for Drugs and Drug Addiction
32 provides information that 5% of the rape victims had been drugged (either with illicit
33 substances, alcohol, or both).[1,2] Interesting work published in 2005 provides
34 information about the toxicological analysis performed on rape victims indicating that
35 alcohol, cannabis, cocaine, benzodiazepines, GHB, and ecstasy were involved in the drug-
36 facilitated sexual assault (DFSA).[3] A more detailed analysis was also performed a few
37 years later (2022) by Skov *et al.* which now shows benzodiazepines as the most frequent
38 DRD used worldwide.[4] The same work also indicates that the toxicological profile of the
39 DFSA victims may include common illicit drugs (amphetamine, methamphetamine,
40 cannabinoids, cocaine, 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine), ketamine, GHB, new
41 psychoactive substances (e.g. methylone, dexmedetomidine), as well as the molecules
42 classified as analgesics, antidepressants, and antipsychotics.[4] This information is
43 especially useful during the sensing scenarios development, as a very complex matrix
44 (composed of intrinsic sample composition enriched by different drug mixtures) should
45 be taken into account.

46 This review paper aims to summarize the current state of the art focused on the
47 electroanalytical detection of DRDs associated with DFC especially DFSA. The benefits and
48 shortcomings of the electroanalytical scenarios are very well described in the scientific
49 literature.[5] The intuitive features of electrochemical sensors are low prices and simple
50 sensing configurations - the final idea is to use this technology in plug-and-play
51 scenarios.[6] We are also convinced that electrochemical sensing is currently being
52 rediscovered due to the commercial availability of very small hardware (potentiostats
53 smaller than the matchbox), software and applications that can provide a binary read-out
54 dedicated to a non-expert user, and finally compatibility with the smartphone
55 technology.[7]

56 From the forensic point of view, the interest of the scientific community in
57 developing electrochemical sensors is mainly focused on the most popular illicit drugs.
58 We encourage readers to explore the updated review papers (published over the last five
59 years) focused on the electroanalytical detection of cocaine [8,9], fentanyl [10,11],
60 amphetamine and its analogs [12] or illicit drugs as a class of analytes [13]. The analysis
61 of the literature suggests that over the last five years number of reports describing illicit
62 drug detection protocols is blooming (cocaine is the molecule still being in the scientific

63 spotlight)[14,15]. Worth noting are the protocols that utilize 3D printing, as this technique
64 brings commonness, reproducibility, and an extremely easy (entire) electrochemical set-
65 up fabrication in R&D laboratories [16,17]. Still, the electroanalytical protocols entirely
66 dedicated to DRD are rare and for many molecules are still missing, not to mention the
67 lack of sensor validation in real samples. With this review paper, we aim to summarize the
68 existing knowledge with a critical evaluation mainly focused on the applicability and
69 functionality of the developed solutions. As seductive drugs are frequently consumed
70 through soft or hard drinks, we underline the reports that are focused on these real
71 samples. We have also identified a few future directions that, along with the conclusions,
72 are expected to address the currently existing knowledge gap.

73 The key findings for this review can be consisted in a few lines. 1. BDZ are the most
74 used and studied DRD in any medium including beverages. 2. The electrochemical
75 behaviors of various NPS are not well characterized and not studied in beverage medium.
76 3. Gamma hydroxybutyrate has the least studied DRD in any sensing matrices due to its
77 poor electrochemical behavior and possesses a significant research gap. 4. A few notable
78 reports of wearable, printed lab-on-chip sensors are appealing and promising for practical
79 adoption to screen DRD in beverages. Lastly, 5. The vast diversity in the chemical
80 composition of beverage medium imposes overwhelming analytical complexity towards
81 DRD screening.

82 **2. Electroanalytical detection of date and rape drugs.**

83 For the past 20 years, the development of analytical tools that enable on-site screening of
84 date rape drugs (DRD) that complement conventional analytical methods has been of
85 great research interest.[18] If not all, most of DRD consists of electrochemically active
86 functional group/s that may undergo redox reactions, and hence, be detected with all
87 electroanalytical tools. In the context of this review, we are focused on rapid (minimal/no
88 pre-sampling, and fast testing time) electroanalytical tools proposed to testify DRD in
89 beverage samples with a few exceptions in rapidness of the system citing the significance
90 of the specific report in the evolution of DRD sensors over the past decade. A
91 comprehensive literature survey using the key word combinations of “benzodiazepine,
92 ketamine, gamma (γ)-hydroxybutyrate, morphine, fentanyl, new psychoactive drugs
93 electrochemical sensors, date and rape drug sensors, beverage, juice, alcohol, soft drinks,
94 and hard drinks” in web-of-science, and Scopus over past ten years reveals about 102

95 electrochemistry-related reports among which BDZ (62%) tops the list as the most
 96 studied DRD. Bio samples (blood, serum, urine, and saliva) are the most studied sensing
 97 matrix (44% of the reports) followed by pharmaceutical formulations and street samples
 98 (24%). Only 22% of the reported electrochemical sensors were targeted to analyse DRD
 99 spiked beverages (water, soft, and hard drinks) which is among the most significant real-
 100 world samples in resolving and preventing DFC. In this respect, BDZs (72% of the reports)
 101 were the most frequently studied drugs, while GHB ends the list. An infographic outlining
 102 the distribution of electrochemical sensors reported for various DRD in different samples
 103 is presented in Figure 1.

104
 105 **Figure 1:** A statistical distribution of electrochemical date and rape drug sensors reported
 106 in the last decade (NPS-New Psychoactive substances, GHB-Gamma Hydroxybuterate).

107 **2.1. Benzodiazepines**

108 Benzodiazepines (BDZ) are a class of psychoactive drugs known for their high
 109 sedative nature. BDZs are prescribed to treat a range of medical conditions ranging from
 110 anxiety to alcohol withdrawal syndrome.[19] These drugs function as central nervous
 111 system depressants by enriching the activity of the benzodiazepine site of the GABA type
 112 A receptor (GABAA receptor) towards the gamma-aminobutyric acid (GABA)
 113 neurotransmitter. The success of Librium/chlordiazepoxide (the first BDZ drug) in 1960s
 114 to treat anxiety, and insomnia triggered the wave of BDZ drug development.[20] Their
 115 strong seductive nature and short life span have made them an ideal component in various
 116 DFC including DFSA[21]. This property is reflected in the research communities' efforts to

117 rapidly screen DRD in complex sample matrices and BDZ (as shown in Figure 1) are the
118 most frequently studied analytes during electrochemical sensors development.

119 The electrochemical behaviour of BDZ drugs is attributed to the azomethine unit
120 in the benzodiazepine skeleton and the presence of other functional groups (such as,
121 amine, nitro, N-oxide, carbonyl, etc.) distributed among the variants of the BDZ core (for
122 chemical structures see Table 1). Therefore, the most common electroanalytical
123 techniques including voltammetry, polarography, and potentiometry are employed to
124 fabricate electrochemical sensing platforms for the rapid screening of BDZs in various
125 sample matrices. In general, the electroanalytical mechanism of BDZ detection involving
126 redox reactions can be classified based on the presence of functional groups as BDZ-Class
127 I (amine and nitro BDZ) and BDZ-Class II (non-nitro/amine BDZ).[22]

128 A typical cyclic voltammogram (CV) of Nitro-BDZ drugs (e.g.: Flunitrazepam,
129 Clonazepam, and Nitrazepam) recorded at carbon-based electrodes initially displays two
130 cathodic peaks R1 (~ -0.7 to -0.9 V vs Ag/AgCl) and R2 (~ -1.1 to -1.3 V vs Ag/AgCl)
131 followed with an anodic peak O1 (~ 0.4 V vs Ag/AgCl) which induce the formation of third
132 cathodic peak R3 (~ -0.3 to -0.28 V vs Ag/AgCl) on the reverse sweep. The overall
133 electrochemical transformation of the process can be described by the equation presented
134 in Figure 2. The cathodic peaks R1 ($+4e^-/+4H^+$) and R2 ($+2e^-/+2H^+$) are attributed to the
135 reduction of nitro, and azomethine groups of Nitro-BDZ into hydroxylamine, and amine
136 groups, respectively. The semi-reversible redox couple of O1 and R3 are the product of
137 hydroxyl amine oxidation (O1, $-2e^-/-2H^+$) into nitroso species and vice versa (R3, $+2e^-$
138 $/+2H^+$). Thanks to its high correlation and interference-free potentials the semi-reversible
139 redox couple of O1/R3 were widely used for the electroanalytical determination of these
140 nitro-BZD drugs, while in some cases the peaks R1 and R2 were used depending upon the
141 sensing matrix. Moreover, the redox couple O1/R3 also appears in the amino-BDZ drugs
142 and its metabolites (e.g.: 7-aminoflunitrazepam, 7-aminonitrazepam) and also have been
143 used for electroanalytical purposes[23,24].

144 The CV of other non-nitro BDZ (e.g.: Diazepam, Midazolam, Alprazolam, and
145 Lorazepam) displays the cathodic peak R2 (~ -1.0 V vs Ag/AgCl) corresponding to the
146 reduction of azomethine groups into respective secondary amine. A subsequent anodic
147 sweeping displays the reduction (R2) induced anodic peak O2 (~ 1.0 V vs Ag/AgCl) which
148 originates due to the ($2e^-/-2H^+$) oxidation of secondary amines to open the diazepine ring

149 of the BDZ skeleton. The CVs and electrochemical reactions of the BDZ derivatives are
150 presented in Figure 2 and scheme 1 [25,26]. Also, a few reports of adsorptive stripping
151 voltammetry and potentiometric sensors describe the electroanalytical detection of BDZ
152 in soft and hard drinks samples.[27–29]

153

154

155 **Scheme 1.** Electrochemical reaction mechanism of **I.** BDZ class I, and **II.** BDZ Class II drugs.

156

157 **Figure 2: I.** CVs of flunitrazepam (BDZ Class I) at different electrodes. Adapted from [30] **II.**
 158 CVs recorded in the absence and presence of diazepam (BDZ Class II). Adapted from [22] **III.**
 159 Schematic representation of the fabrication of AGO-Cu/SPCE-based Flunitrazepam sensor
 160 applied for fruit juice analyses. Adapted from [31]. **IV.** (A) Laser-scribing on
 161 graphene/polyetherimide, (B) SEM morphology of Laser-scribed graphene, (C) SEM
 162 tomography of polyetherimide (D) Chemical structure of diazepam and midazolam (E)
 163 Background corrected SWV curves of 2.5-100 μM of diazepam recorded at 0.1M BRB pH 4.0.
 164 Adapted from [25]. **V.** (A) Schematic representation of midazolam sensor sampling at boron
 165 doped diamond electrode (BDDE), (B) Electrochemical reduction mechanism of midazolam
 166 at BDDE, (C) CVs obtained for 1 mM MID in 0.12 M BRB at pH=2.0. Adapted from [32]. **VI.**
 167 (A) Schematic representation of the fabrication of CoOOH-rGO/SPCE portable
 168 electrochemical sensor for clonazepam, (B) Electrochemical reduction mechanism of

169 *clonazepam at CoOOH-rGO/SPCE, (C) DPV analysis of CoOOH-rGO/SPCE for 0.1-350 μM of*
170 *clonazepam in 0.005 M K₃ Fe(CN)₆^{3-/4-} PBS pH 7.4 Adapted form [33].*

171 **2.1.1. Voltametric sensing of Benzodiazepines**

172 Flunitrazepam (FNZ) is among the most studied BDZ in soft and hard drinks. Its
173 high popularity in DFC including DFSA has led to its withdrawal from the EU market in
174 2007 [19,20]. Clonazepam (CNZ) and Nitrazepam (NTZ) are two other profound nitro-
175 BDZ drugs. The chemical structure of all three drugs consists of azomethine, carbonyl, and
176 nitro groups that enable the BDZ-Class I electrochemical sensing mechanism.

177 Electrochemical detection of NTZ and FNZ were reported by Hart *et al.* on a simple
178 screen-printed carbon electrode (SPCE) using CV. Both drugs displayed cathodic (R1, R2,
179 and R3) and anodic (O1) peaks found between -1.5 V, and +0.5 V (repetitive cycling). A
180 simple voltammetric sensor was developed by dropping a small volume of sample (10 -
181 100 μL) onto the surface of SPCE, drying step, followed by dissolution in PB supporting
182 electrolyte. NTZ detection was based on O1 peak showing a liner relationship at
183 micromolar range (LOD = 6.3 μM). The authors proved that NTZ can be detected in Pepsi
184 Max, Vodka Kick Ice Cherry, Absinthe, and brandy with adequate recovery rates [34]. In
185 2012, Banks *et al.* used screen-printed graphite electrodes (SPGE) to directly detect FNZ
186 in Coca Cola™ and the alcopop WKD™. These works has fixed the fundamental obstacle
187 of colorimetric tools toward rapid screening of DRD in colored beverage samples, through
188 a simple ready-to-use electrochemical platform [35]. The challenge remaining to be solved
189 was the fluctuating performance of different SPE. Relatively straightforward modification
190 of SPCE with AGO-Cu provided a detection range of 0.4-140.0 μM for FNZ detection and
191 was applied for spiked fruit juice analysis (Figure 2 III) [31].

192 These and many more works provide different protocols for BDZs detection which
193 are usually affected by the addition of different types of nanomaterials serving as the
194 carbon-based (most frequently) electrode modification delivered a detection limits of few
195 micromoles. Meanwhile, GCE electrode modified with TiO₂@CuO@ N doped rGO and
196 poly(L-cysteine) pushed the LOD down to nanomoles (0.3 nM) for FNZ detection. The real-
197 world applicability of the developed sensor was demonstrated in Tourtel Malt, Coca-Cola
198 drink, and human plasma with recovery rates of 90.0–104.0 % [36]. Later, Prodromidis et
199 al. reported a low-cost lab-on-a-screen-printed electrochemical cell (SPC) based on iron-

200 sparked graphite working electrode modified with glucose oxidase (GOx) and glucose
201 hydrogel droplets (GluHD) for the detection of FNZ. Iron-spark modification of SPE
202 (FeSPE) has increased the current response by 3-fold compared with that of the bare SPE.
203 In addition, the GOx enabled the *in-situ* enzymatic deoxygenation process to improve the
204 analytical resolution by minimizing the background currents limiting nitro group
205 reduction. Altogether this method enabled interference-free voltammetric detection of
206 FNZ in various samples to sub-micromolar levels (LOD- 15 nM) [24]. Especially exciting
207 is the report by Kokkinos *et. al.* who developed a 3D-printed wearable e-finger
208 electrochemical cell to screen multiple DRDs in beverage samples. Under optimized
209 conditions, the wearable e-finger displayed the CVs signature of BDZ-Class I with
210 reduction peaks of 7-nitro, and hydroxylamine groups found for FNZ. The sensing unit was
211 validated on undiluted whiskey, vodka, gin, and beer [37].

212 Early report of CNZ detection in wine samples was reported by Honeychurch et al.
213 in 2016, through adsorptive stripping voltammetry on a screen-printed carbon electrode.
214 The CNZ displayed typical CVs of BDZ-Class I on SPCE with peak O1 shown linear
215 relationship with CNZ concentration of few micromoles and used to determine CNZ spiked
216 in wine and serum samples [38]. The specific pre-sampling procedures of the study is an
217 obstacle to be addressed for practicality. In sequence, a cobalt oxyhydroxide (CoOOH)
218 nanoflakes self-assembled reduced graphene oxide (rGO) nanocomposite modified SPCE
219 (CoOOH-rGO/SPCE) was also reported for the determination of CNZ in different beverages
220 (Coca Cola, Real Juice, Beer, and Wine) samples with a similar analytical range paired with
221 high sensitivity ($0.054 \mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$), and recovery rates (87–115%)(Figure 2 VI) [33].
222 While, large interference from uric acid, urea, glucose, K^+ and Na^+ ions deters the practical
223 reliability of the CoOOH-rGO/SPCE sensor. Meanwhile, Limbut et al. proposed an
224 electrochemically pre-treated glassy carbon electrode (GCE) probe for high sensitive
225 determination of CNZ spiked in beverage samples through adsorptive cathodic stripping
226 voltammetry(AdCSV). The AdCSV peak currents at EC-GCE was linear against increasing
227 concentration of CNZ between 79 nM to 4.7 μM with a detection limit of 60 nM extending
228 the analytical figures from sub-micromoles to nanomolar concentrations. Moreover, the
229 EC-GCE was used to determine the CNZ in spiked beverage samples with an impressive
230 recovery rate of 98 to 102 % [39].

231 Diazepam (DIZ), Lorazepam (LRZ), Midazolam (MDZ) and Alprazolam (ALZ) are
232 the most common non-nitro/amino BDZ with closely related chemical structures. LRZ
233 possesses one Cl and OH groups in addition to the single Cl substituent in the DIZ skeleton
234 while the MDZ and ALZ possess imidazole and triazine rings in their backbone. The typical
235 voltammetric features of these drugs follows BDZ-Class II mechanism which primarily
236 focuses on the reduction of azomethine (R2) and oxidation of secondary amine to open
237 the diazepine ring (O2). Differences in the electrochemical properties of these drugs, their
238 redox behaviour affected by different electrode materials, and the effect of the real sample
239 matrix on the resulting electroanalytical output was studied in a few works. Kevin *et al.*
240 in 2013 used simple SPCE along with adsorptive stripping voltammetry to detect DIZ in
241 fortified Red Russian Ice Cherry, vodka-based alcohol pop containing 4% v/v ethanol, and
242 PepsiMax (alcohol-free) [40]. Prakash *et al.*, proposed a graphene oxide/lysine (GO/lys)
243 composite modified GCE for rapid sub-micromolar detection of DIZ in Juice, cola, whisky,
244 and wine without any sample pretreatments with adequate selectivity and rates of
245 recovery [41]. William *et al.* fabricated laser-scribed graphene (LSG) on polyetherimide
246 (PEI) substrate for portable electrochemical detection of diazepam (DIZ) and midazolam
247 (MDZ) in beverage samples using square wave voltammetry (SWV) (Figure 2 IV). The PEI-
248 LSG based DIZ and MDZ sensor has shown a linear range up to 100 μM with sub
249 micromolar detection and quantification limits. Further, the PEI-LSG sensor was
250 successful in the screening of DIZ and MDZ in juice, whisky, and sugarcane spirit with
251 recoveries ranging from 97.1% to 117.2% for DIZ and. 92.2% to 114.3% for MDZ[25]. In
252 sequence, Rocha *et al.* used boron-doped diamond electrode (BDDE) for selective MDZ
253 detection in beverage samples (vodka, whiskey, and red wine) (Figure 2 V). The
254 electroanalytical performance of MDZ at BDDE in vodka, whisky, and red wine samples
255 was studied individually and delivered a dynamic range at lower micromoles with sub-
256 micromolar detection limits [32]. Finally, the detection of LRZ in water, urine, and hair
257 samples at trace levels with notable selectivity and recovery [42,43], or FNZ spiked in
258 Coca-cola, Fanta, Sprite, Red Bull, Barbican, and Nestle purelife water [27,44]also exist,
259 and the corresponding electroanalytical parameters (along with other examples) are
260 summarized in **Table 1**.

261 We have also reported an alternative electroanalytical detection of clozapine (CZ)
262 at electrified liquid-liquid interface (eLLI). The eLLI composed of two immiscible
263 solutions of 10mM NaCl/10mM HCl with 10% EtOH (v/v) placed on top of 5 mM

264 bis(triphenylphosphoranylidene)ammonium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate
265 (BTTPA⁺TPBCl⁻) in 1,2-dichloroethane. The detection was based on the transfer of CZ from
266 the aqueous to the organic phase and was studied using ion-transfer voltammetry.
267 Furthermore, the practical feasibility of the system was demonstrated in determining CZ
268 spiked in apple juice, apple juice + vodka, vodka, wine, and beer samples with analytical
269 performance on par with that of chromatographic tools[45]. This have been the first
270 report on the use of eLLI towards electroanalytical detection of BDZ in soft and hard
271 drinks samples that deliver promising results for an alternative approach for the design
272 of electrochemical sensors. Detection of BDZs at the eLLI is an interesting approach that
273 can be extrapolated to detect other molecules of this family based on the ion transfer and
274 not the redox reactions.[46]

275 In summary, starting from a decade ago with simple electrode activation protocols
276 to printing custom-made electrochemical cells the electroanalytical tools have been
277 proven to be fully useful in BDZ drug detection in various samples represented by soft and
278 hard drinks. Meanwhile, the design of electrochemical units primarily focused on
279 fabricating comprehensive electrochemical devices (Lab-on-chip,
280 miniaturized/microfluidic electrochemical cells, wearable electrochemical devices) is still
281 to be incorporated, developed, and studied. We believe that thanks to the recent growth
282 in fabrication technologies (mainly 3D printings), and internet-of-things (IOT) on-site
283 periodic detection protocols (based on electrochemistry) for BDZ detection will be soon
284 provided and applied.[16]

285 **2.2. Ketamine**

286 Ketamine (KT) is a derivative of chlorophenol with the blocking action on the N-methyl-
287 d-aspartate (NMDA) receptors in neural cells[47]. It is a tasteless, odourless and
288 colourless anaesthetic drug having sedative properties[48]. In low doses, it can
289 demonstrate clinical significance in the treatment of depression [49] and pain-processing
290 neurons related to the spinal cord and brain[50]. KT has become a popular illicit drug[51]
291 (known as e.g. “K-powder”) which may also be used for DFSA[37] . This section will
292 illustrate and describe the electroanalytical protocols for KT detection with the focus
293 given to beverages used as the real matrix.

294 **2.2.1. Detection of ketamine in beverages**

295 Table 1 enlists sensors fabricated for the electrochemical detection of KT in beverages
296 with important parameters including LOD, LDR, and their potential applications in testing
297 alcoholic and non-alcoholic beverages. In this chapter, we will critically discuss only a few
298 examples that were used for KT detection. Lledo-Fernandez *et al.* were the first to report
299 electroanalytical detection of KT using the electrochemiluminescence (ECL) technique
300 employing $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ as ECL probe. The sensing unit was based on a conventional three-
301 electrode system with GCE serving as the working electrode placed over a miniaturized
302 photomultiplier tube having ECL sensitivity ~ 610 nm. The detection mechanism was
303 typical and relied on the $[\text{Ru}(\text{bpy})_3]^{2+}$ regeneration by the tertiary amine group from the
304 KT structure. Figure 3(IA) depicts the ECL signal in the presence and absence of KT[52].
305 A linear detection range from $0.21 \mu\text{M}$ to $8.41 \mu\text{M}$ was achieved with a low detection limit
306 of $0.14 \mu\text{M}$. This method's utility was verified in discrimination between KT enantiomers
307 and detection in Gordon's Gin & Tonic (alcoholic beverage, Figure 3(IB)) . Narang *et al.*
308 proposed a point-of-care nano-hybrid-based electrochemical microfluidic paper-based
309 analytical device (E μ PAD) for the detection of KT. Fabrication involved computer-aided
310 design, Whatman no. 1 filter paper (support), and wax-based ink for channel printing (see
311 Figure 3(IIA)). Counter and working electrodes were prepared using conducting carbon
312 ink. Although the WE was modified with graphene oxide (GO) nanoflakes (improving
313 electrode conductivity) and zeolites crystal (Zeo, bringing large surface area) the
314 voltammetric features of the obtained configuration were burdened with significant
315 resistance (see Figure 3(IIB)) which will surely limit the practical applications.
316 Nevertheless, the authors claim that E μ PAD can be used to detect KT in the presence of
317 the most common interfering agents including glucose, fructose, maltose, AA,
318 hydrocortisone, gentamycine, K^+ , Na^+ , Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Fe^{3+} . It was also used for the direct
319 detection of KT in alcoholic (e.g. whisky) and non-alcoholic (orange juice) beverages [53].

320

321 **Figure 3. I.** Electrochemiluminescence (ECL) based electroanalytical detection of Ketamine
 322 in alcoholic beverages (A) ECL signal intensity without and without Ketamine, and (B)
 323 calibration plot for ketamine recorded in Gordon Gin & amp; Tonic solution. Adapted from
 324 [52]. **II.** Microfluidic paper-based analytical device (E μ PADs) for the Ketamine detection (A)
 325 E μ PAD modified with nanocrystals of zeolites (Zeo) and graphene oxide, and (B) CVs of
 326 modified electrode using increasing concentrations (0.01-5 μ M) of Ketamine. Adapted from
 327 [53]. **III.** Core-shell molecularly imprinted polymer (MIP) screen-printed sensor for the
 328 Ketamine detection. (A) sensor fabrication steps, and (B) linear relationship between the
 329 potential and increasing ketamine concentrations (1.0 μ M to 10 mM). Adapted from [54]. **IV.**
 330 Wearable electrochemical sensor for the Ketamine detection in alcoholic beverages (A) 3D-
 331 printed electrochemical-finger based sensing platform, and (B) differential pulse
 332 voltammograms (DPV) recorded with the e-finger obtained in untreated and undiluted
 333 whiskey before (red line) and after (black line) spiking with 0.5 mM Ketamine. The inset is
 334 the baseline corrected DPVs at the e-finger for corresponding calibration plot. Adapted
 335 from[37].

336 Another elegant example of KT detection comes from the work of Soliman *et al.* Here, the
 337 SPCE covered with polyaniline was modified with rather a complex assembly of
 338 nanomaterials. The ketamine molecularly imprinted polymer (copolymerized methacrylic
 339 acid and ethylene glycol dimethacrylate) was placed over silica nanoparticles that were
 340 further incorporated into the polyvinylchloride membrane (see Figure 3(IIIA)). The

341 electroanalytical evaluation of the sensors provided LOD and LOQ equal to 0.93 μM and
342 1.00 μM , respectively. A selectivity study was done with the common chemical species
343 such as Na^+ , K^+ , Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Quetiapine. The authors also proved that their sensing
344 interface can be directly used to detect KT in non-alcoholic beverages (e.g. juices) [54]. We
345 are also happy to underline the work of Poulladofonou *et al.* who fabricated 3D printed
346 wearable electronic finger (e-finger) in a fully “Do-it-Yourself” manner. They have used an
347 accessible and cheap 3D printer, a portable potentiostat that was integrated with the
348 smartphone, and two printing filaments (conductive polylactic acid and acrylonitrile
349 butadiene styrene) to provide a fully functional device for KT detection in alcoholic
350 beverages such as whiskey, vodka, gin, and beer Figure 3(IVA). DPV recorded in the
351 presence of KT using an e-finger depicts an oxidation signal at $\approx + 1.5$ V that was further
352 used for quantification as shown in the inset of Figure 3(IVB) showing a series of DPVs
353 recorded in spiked and not treated alcoholic samples. Even though the printed device can
354 be considered disposable, the authors proved that it is stable for up to 12 days and can be
355 used for KT detection in the presence of buscopan, ketamidol, and depon [37].
356 Electroanalytical protocols for the KT detection are mostly focused on body fluids Table
357 S1. Since many working protocols were already developed, their validation in the soft and
358 hard drinks seems to be an intuitive direction.

359 **2.3. New Psychoactive Substances**

360 New Psychoactive Substances (NPS) are drugs that are frequently referred to as
361 *legal highs* or *legal drugs*. NPSs encompass a broad list of chemical structures, including
362 synthetic cannabinoids, fentanyl analogs, synthetic cathinones, tryptamines, and others.
363 These substances often elicit psychoactive effects akin to well-known illicit drugs such as
364 cannabis, ecstasy, and LSD. Many of the NPSs are used directly as DRD or are added to the
365 illicit drug formulations. Regarding the use of electrochemical techniques for detecting
366 NPSs, there is a limited number of literature reports, indicating significant potential for
367 expansion in this area. Those available have been thoroughly analyzed and are
368 incorporated into Tables 1 and S1. Among these publications, only one focuses on
369 detecting morphine in beverages (milk and coffee)[55]. The remaining studies center
370 around determining substances in model samples[56], artificial or spiked human body
371 fluids (such as serum[57], urine[58], and plasma[59]), synthetic urine[60], street
372 samples[61], pharmaceutical formulations[59,62], and blotting papers[63].

373

374 **Fig. 4 I.** shows the platforms for the determination of morphine using (A) a patterned flash
 375 foam stamp and (B) SWCNTs three-electrode arrays on a PVDF membrane; (C) DPV plots for
 376 the detection of morphine in coffee (D) and morphine in skimmed milk samples by the
 377 SWCNTs-based sensor: a. food samples without morphine; b. morphine in the PBS buffer; c.
 378 morphine in food samples. Adopted from [55] **II.** Lab-on-a-Glove concept for on-site
 379 detection of fentanyl; (A) A glove equipped with an ionic liquid/MWCNT modified measuring
 380 finger and sample collector; (B) Gloved sensor with a portable electroanalyzer (C) Image
 381 showing suspicious sample collection in powder phase. (D) Joining of thumb (collector) and
 382 sensing finger after swiping a powder sample; inset shows the voltammograms of direct
 383 fentanyl detection. Adopted from [56] **III.** Schematic representation of the fabrication of LCE
 384 sensor for fentanyl determination. Adopted from [57].

385 While the focus of this work is on the electrochemical analysis of psychoactive
 386 substances in beverages, this chapter will also discuss the electroanalysis of NPSs which
 387 are considered DRDs. In 2022, Yang *et al.* devised a straightforward filtration method for
 388 the scalable production of disposable single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWCNTs)-based
 389 antifouling electrochemical sensors for detecting morphine in unprocessed coffee and
 390 milk [55]. The sensor manufacturing process involved multiple steps. Initially, electrode
 391 templates were printed on kraft paper using a standard office printer. Subsequently, the
 392 template was secured in a glass clamp alongside a fresh stamp made of photosensitive

393 foam and exposed to UV light in a flash stamping machine. The resulting stencil, with
394 distinct patterns (see Figure 4 IA), underwent treatment with a polydimethylsiloxane
395 (PDMS) prepolymer solution to imprint the patterns under pressure onto a polyvinylidene
396 fluoride (PVDF) membrane covered with the SWCNTs (Figure 4 IB). From the entire
397 matrix, a specific set of electrodes was cut, and sealed with PVC tape, and the reference
398 electrode was coated with Ag/AgCl conductive paste, rendering it ready for morphine
399 detection. A linear relationship was determined over a concentration range of 0.7 to 350
400 μM and a detection limit was 0.22 μM . In addition, the stability and reproducibility of the
401 developed sensors were investigated, and an extensive analysis of the influence of a total
402 of 21 potentially interfering substances and ions was carried out and showed no
403 significant effect on the morphine-derived signal. Electrochemical experiments utilizing
404 the newly developed sensors were carried out on both instant coffee and skimmed milk
405 samples. Figure 4 IC, shows resulting voltammetric curves, with (a) representing the
406 coffee sample without morphine addition, displaying a distinct strong oxidation peak at
407 0.13 V. Curve (b) corresponds to the PBS solution with the addition of morphine, revealing
408 an oxidation peak at 0.33 V, while curve (c) was recorded post morphine addition to the
409 coffee solution. Similarly, the graph in Figure 4 ID, illustrating results from electrochemical
410 tests conducted in skimmed milk. Although the proposed protocol was successful the
411 presence of proteins and fats necessitates the development of additional antifouling
412 interfaces.

413 Very interesting is the work by Barfidokht *et al.*, [56] which addresses the rapid detection
414 of fentanyl *in situ* with the transducing element placed on the tip of glove. The sensors was
415 based on the flexible screen-printed carbon electrodes modified with multi-walled carbon
416 nanotubes (MWCNT) and a room-temperature ionic liquid (IL, 4-(3-butyl-1-
417 imidazolium)-1-butanefulfonate (Figure 4 IIA and C). The glove sensor facilitates the
418 direct oxidation of fentanyl in both liquid (in 0.1 M PBS, pH 7.4) and powder (conducting
419 agarose hydrogel that covers the sensing finger was used as an electrolyte) forms,
420 achieving a detection limit of 10 μM through the square wave voltammetry technique
421 (SWV) (Figure 4 IID). By combining sampling on the thumb and detection on the index
422 fingers, this integration facilitates swift screening of fentanyl, even in the presence of
423 various cutting agents (acetaminophen, caffeine, and glucose). We are sure that this
424 approach could find applications in soft and hard drinks analysis, especially since the

425 "Lab-on-a-Glove" sensor can be paired with the portable electrochemical analyzer
426 (EmStat3 Blue) (Figure 4 IIB).

427 In the context of fentanyl sensing, Mishra *et al.*[57] introduced a new approach utilizing
428 laser-induced nanoporous carbon (LCE) structures directly applied to commercially
429 available polyimide sheets. The set-up involving a polyimide sheet, Ag/AgCl paste, and
430 silicone used as insulation is shown in Figure 4 III. Before fentanyl determination, it was
431 essential to clean the surfaces of the LCE electrodes with ethanol and deionized water,
432 followed by drying with pure nitrogen. These sensors facilitated fentanyl determination
433 through SWV, exhibiting a detection limit of 1 μM . The measurable signal from fentanyl
434 appeared at a potential of +0.526 V, within the clinically relevant working range of 20-200
435 μM , demonstrating consistent performance in both PBS and serum samples. None of the
436 tested potentially interfering substances (theophylline, acetaminophen, ascorbic acid, uric
437 acid, and caffeine) significantly influenced the analyte signal.

438 Electroanalysis is a useful tool in the context of NPSs. Due to the relatively small number
439 of scientific articles focused on these molecules, we can see a lot of place for improvement,
440 especially in the detection of these substances in beverages. An asset worth highlighting
441 is the effectiveness of the determination of psychoactive substances despite the presence
442 of potential cutting substances. None of the review work indicated the problems related
443 to the interfering species.

444 **2.4. Gamma(γ)-hydroxy butyrate**

445 γ -hydroxybutyrate (GHB) is an endogenous neurotransmitter mainly present in the
446 mammalian brain. GHB is one of the most notorious DRD with quick and strong if not the
447 quickest and strongest sedative effect through its rapid inhibition of the central nervous
448 system [64]. The symptoms of GHB intoxication include but are not limited to amnesia,
449 disinhibition, dizziness, memory loss, and muscle suppression and relaxation. GHB is a
450 colorless and odourless substance completely soluble in water and alcohols making it
451 untraceable once mixed in common drinking water or beverages. Once ingested GHB is
452 quickly eliminated from the body with a truly short plasma half-life period of 30-50
453 minutes. Moreover, only ~ 1 -5 % of the GHB dose can be recovered from the urine samples
454 within 3-10 hr from its ingestion. For instance, to instigate sedative effects a drink volume
455 of ~ 150 mL must be spiked with about (and only) $10 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ of GHB (~ 100 mM) and the

456 possibility of finding a maximum dose of GBH in the urine samples of the victim for next
457 3-10hr is collectively equal to only ~ 5 mM. This explains the analytical complexity of GHB
458 detection [65]. To this date, complex analytical methods are used for the analysis of GHB
459 in blood and urine samples of the victims in forensic testing. However, these are overly
460 complex and require skilled professionals and specific technological equipment. Most
461 importantly all these methods are developed for GHB detection post-ingestion and not to
462 prevent GHB-induced DFC. At this trend, there are not many forensic tools available to
463 detect GHB in suspicious samples to prevent DFC including DFSA in real-time.
464 Furthermore, unlike other DRD discussed earlier, GHB is not electrochemically active (i.e.,
465 non-redox active) under normal conditions at carbon (and many others) electrodes and
466 hence its electrochemical detection is seldom. The electrochemical works that do exist are
467 focused on the electrochemical mechanistic and not analytical aspects [66–68]. So far, only
468 one report on electroanalytical GHB sensor development was released by Rodriguez *et al.*
469 in 2018 [69]. They have studied the electrooxidation of GHB and ethanol on a glassy
470 carbon/platinum nanoparticles/polyvinyl alcohol (GC/PtNPs/PVA) modified electrode in
471 a weakly acidic medium through CV and chronoamperometry. The results of CVs
472 investigation revealed that GHB significantly suppressed the oxidation peak currents of
473 ethanol (once added to the mixture) as both alcoholic groups of GHB and EtOH compete
474 for the active sites of Pt according to a Langmuir-type expression. This observation
475 supports the idea, that GHB dominates the electrocatalytic activity of Pt over other
476 commonly active species like alcohol due to the presence of carboxylic acid group and
477 leading to the fall of current densities of ethanol oxidation (Figure 5 III). This depression
478 in the current density attributed to ethanol oxidation in the presence of GHB was used for
479 the determination of GHB in the concentration range of 1 and 75 mM. The authors have
480 evaluated the practical feasibility of the GC/PtNPs/PVA in alcoholic drinks (vodka,
481 lemonade + vodka, gin, rum, tequila, and whisky) spiked with GHB and obtained recovery
482 (80 -120 %) and precision for intra (RSD= 0.99 - 5.99%; n=9) and inter-assay (RSD=1.29
483 - 6.49%; n=3 days) meeting the standards of the presumptive analysis.

484 The limited reports on the electroanalytical detection of GHB (not limited to hard/soft
485 drinks, as in any sample matrices) indicate great potential and need for research in this
486 direction. Unlike other DRDs discussed earlier, the endogenous nature of GHB made its
487 ingestion indistinguishable during forensic analysis of biosamples retrieved from DFC
488 victims including DFSA. Therefore, analytical tools that can be used to detect GHB in food

489 and drinks on-site are crucial. At present, colorimetric sensors emerging as a promising
490 tool for on-site screening of GHB are not suitable for colored beverages. As such, platforms
491 that enable rapid on-site screening of GHB in food and drinks require major research focus
492 to prevent GHB-associated DFC.

493
494 **Figure 5:** CVs of **I.** GHB, **II.** EtOH, and **III.** GHB in whisky samples. Reproduced from [69].

495 3. Other significant reports.

496 Some specific design principles and significant analytical performance towards
497 electroanalytical DRD sensing falling beyond the applied classification are worth special
498 attention.

499 For instance, differential pulse adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetry
500 (PDAdCSV) of BDZ on hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) has shown a great
501 potential towards BDZ (ALZ [28], CNZ, and DIZ [29]) detection in water samples. The
502 technique delivered impressive analytical parameters such as high sensitivity, wide
503 dynamic range, low LOD, LOQ, and high recoveries. Despite all its analytical merits the
504 technique was not popularized due to its inherent downsides such as larger size,
505 complicated electronics and mechanics for precise drop generation, and the use of toxic
506 mercury [70]. These irreparable shortfalls of HMDE eventually halt its opportunities to be
507 an alternative electroanalytical platform for DRD sensing.

508 Similarly, Karolien *et al.* reported a readily available disposable SPE modified with
509 sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) for electrochemical detection of multiple DRD (cocaine,
510 heroin, MDMA, Cl-PVP, and KT) in oral fluids. The simple SDS modification significantly
511 magnifies the analytical signals by 3 to 6 folds, and delivers high accuracy (RSD 1.8 - 5.3
512 %)[71]. This work presented the use of a surfactant-mediated solution as potent modifier
513 for the electrocatalytic detection of DRD over renowned nanocomposites. A few significant

514 reports of electrochemical DRD sensors studied non-beverage matrices are surveyed and
515 presented as Table S1 in the supporting information.

516 **4. Challenges and Future perspectives**

517 This article summarizes recent progress in the development of electrochemical sensors
518 to detect DRD in soft and hard drink samples. The core challenges identified for the given
519 topic cover: 1. Analytical complexity of the real samples. 2. Complex testing procedures
520 and site of investigation. 3. Sensing units and components that should be cheap, portable,
521 disposable, miniaturized, and display high precision and reliability. 4. Electroanalysis of
522 GHB, morphine, and new psychoactive substances in hard and soft drinks samples.

523 The electroanalytical complexity of DRD in beverage samples is obvious citing the
524 chemical composition of various drink samples including but not limited to sugars,
525 flavoring agents, amino acids, vitamins, proteins, alkaloids, food colors, alcohol, etc. Much
526 of these co-existing species are electroactive and pose interfering electrochemical signals,
527 and/or cause electrode fouling that promptly reduces electrocatalytic behaviour of the
528 sensor towards target DRD. Resolving these obstacles leads us to challenge 2 which
529 mandates complex pre-sampling procedures. Even though there are reports on the simple
530 use of SPCE and activated GCE towards DRD sensing without any sample pretreatments
531 these reports are not very successful and are compromised by chemical interference or
532 surface fouling. On the other hand, the complex sampling procedures are not suitable for
533 on-site screening of DRD in beverage samples supplied in public gatherings, partying,
534 bars, etc. which are the common spots of DRD spiking. Resolving these issues needs an
535 innovative design of electrochemical systems that minimize sample volume, sampling
536 steps, and the sample preparation time. The ultimate goal is to offer a design that can be
537 used in a plug-and-play manner. Initial reports on the wearable e-finger multidrug sensor
538 (FNZ, KT, and SCO), the wearable glove-based sensor for detecting fentanyl, or other
539 disposable and miniaturized drop volume sensors printed/scribed on various substrates
540 (for BDZ, KT, fentanyl) discussed in this article seems to be seminal in this respect.

541 To our surprise the knowledge gap on the electroanalytical behavior of GHB, morphine,
542 fentanyl and other NPS in beverage samples is obvious and requires further effect. This
543 lack of information is due to the combination of all three obstacles discussed earlier as
544 these substances possess significant analytical complexity thanks to their chemical and

545 electrochemical behavior. Therefore, there is an immense need and scope for the design
546 of novel electroanalytical platforms that resolve the obstacles in analytical principles,
547 operational methods, and fabrication techniques to enable the rapid determination of
548 these substances in various samples associated with DFC. Finally, the massive profiling of
549 the beverage's electroanalytical response on a variety of transducing elements would
550 provide a large amount of data that could be used for the presumptive detection of DRD,
551 as the simple electrochemical profile of the real sample in the presence and in the absence
552 of the drug could be treated as the analytical information. A comprehensive summery on
553 the existing electroanalytical methodologies, its analytical milestones, limitations, and
554 possible remedies directing at future perspectives in rapid on-site detection of DRD in
555 beverages are listed and presented as Table 2.

556 **5. Conclusions**

557 This review presents recent progress in the design and development of electroanalytical
558 platforms towards rapid on-site screening of date-rape-drugs (DRD) in beverage samples.
559 This field attracted the attention of scientists only in the last decade. We have found that
560 bio samples, pharmaceutical formulations, and formulated street samples are the most
561 studied real-samples covering about 68% of all published reports. Around 22% of the
562 works evaluated the utility of the electroanalytical sensing solutions for DRD detection in
563 spiked beverages. Benzodiazepines top the list of the most studied DRD when it comes to
564 the overall number of reports and beverage analyses. Successively, this review staged a
565 critical analysis of the design fabrication and analytical performance of existing
566 electroanalytical DRD sensors. We guide the reader through the common protocols
567 employing screen-printed electrodes to advanced solutions that are based on the lab-on-
568 chip, glove, and e-finger technology. Many published reports offer ready-to-use protocols
569 with high sensitivity, analytical reliability, and reproducibility. The exponential growth in
570 the development of DRD sensors over the past decade is not distributed equally as we
571 underlined a serious lack of research attention toward the design of electroanalytical
572 platforms that have the potential to study new psychoactive substances and gamma-
573 hydroxy butyrate in beverage samples. In essence, this review illustrates periodical
574 progress in the current state-of-art electrochemical sensors reported for rapid screening
575 of DRD in beverage samples but also highlights the existence of a knowledge gap in certain
576 areas to build a course for future advancements in the field.

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- 863

864 **Table 1:** Analytical performances of the reported electrochemical date and rape sensors studied at beverage matrix.

Date and Rape Drug	Technique	Signal Transducer	Detection Condition	LDR	LOD	Tested Interferons	Tested Real samples	Ref.	Comments
Flunitrazepam/ Rohypnol 	DPV	GOx/GluHD-FeSPCE	Reduction $E_p = -0.58$ V 0.1 M PBS pH 7.0	0.05 – 10 μ M	0.015 μ M	Dissolved oxygen	Pepsi cola, Gin, Vodka, Whisky, Tequila, Rum	[30]	A First-of-kind enzymatic transducer based SPCE is proposed.
	DPV	Wearable 3D printed electrochemical finger (e-finger)	Reduction $aE_p = -0.93$ V 0.1 M PB pH 7.4	6.3 – 51 μ M	0.2 – 0.3 μ M	Buscopan, Ketamidol, Depon	Whiskey, Gin Vodka, Beer.	[37]	(i) 3D-printed wearable device for on-the-spot self-checking and onsite forensic investigation.
	DPV	TiO ₂ @CuO-N-rGO/poly (L-Cys)/GCE	Oxidation $E_p = +0.65$ V	1 nM – 50 μ M	0.3 nM	Sodium, iron, chloride, sulfate,	Tourtel Malt, Pepsi Cola	[36]	S: 0.288 μ A μ M ⁻¹

			0.04 M BRB pH 3.0			nitrate, citric acid, sucrose, fructose, dopamine, and uric acid			
	DPV	AGO-Cu/SPCE	Oxidation $E_p = +0.25$ V 0.04 M BRB pH 7.0	0.4–140 μ M	0.13 μ M	Na^+ , Cl^- , Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , NO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , NH_4^+ , Fe^{2+} and CO_3^{2-}	Fruit juice	[31]	S: 0.405 $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$
	CV	SPCE	Reduction $E_p = -0.85$ V 4 M KCl	7.9 – 79.8 μ M	1.8 – 14.6 μ M	GHB, Ketamine, and Scopolamine.	Whiskey, Vodka, and Gin.	[44]	LOQ: 1.7- 3.5 S: 0.142 $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$
Clonazepam 	DPV	CoOOH-rGO /GCE	Reduction $E_p = +0.11$ V 0.005 M $\text{K}_3\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6^{3-/4-}$ PBS pH 7.4	0.1–350 μ M	38 nM	L-cysteine, uric acid, urea, glucose, ascorbic acid,	Juice, cola, beer, wine	[33]	S: 0.054 $\mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$

						Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , and SO ₄ ²⁻			
ASV	C10903P14 ink/SPCE	Oxidation E _p = -1.5V, 60s 10% EtOH in 0.1 M PB pH 7.0	6.5 – 25.5 μM	6.2 μM	Not studied	Wine	[38]	S: 6.9 nA μM ⁻¹	
AdCSV	EP-GCE	Reduction E _p = -0.56 V 0.1 M PB pH 7.0	79.8 nM – 4.7 μM	60 nM	Not studied	Full Moon, Smirnoff and drinking water	[39]	LOQ: 0.199 μM S: 10.04 μA μM ⁻¹	
PDA CSV	HMDE	Reduction E _p = -0.41 V 0.1M PB pH 8.0	2.0 – 47.88 nM	0.6 nM	Not studied	Natural water		S: 0.045 nA nM ⁻¹	

<p>Nitrazepam</p>	AdSV	SPCE	Oxidation $E_p = -0.1$ V 10% EtOH in 0.1M PB pH 7.0	50.1 - 600 μ M	6.3 μ M	Aspirin, gamma- butyrolactone, and Paracetamol	Pepsi Max, Vodka Kick Ice Cherry, Absinthe, brandy.	[34]	S: 15.2 nA μ M ⁻¹
<p>Diazepam</p>	DPV	GO/lysine/GCE	Reduction $E_p = -0.86$ V 0.1M PB pH 7.0	0.17- 50 mM	0.046 mM	Glucose, Uric acid, and Nitrazepam.	Juice, cola, whisky, wine	[41]	LOQ:156 nM S: 0.209 μ A μ M ⁻¹
	ASV-DPV	SPCE	Oxidation $E_p = +1.0$ V 10% EtOH in 0.1 M PB pH 6.0	24.9 - 1000 mM	6.3 mM	Aspartame Ascorbic acid, Citric acid, and Paracetamol.	PepsiMax, Vodka Cherry alcopop	[40]	S: 7.4 nA μ M ⁻¹

	SWV	PEI-LSG	Reduction $E_p = -1.15$ V 0.1M BRB pH 4.0	2.5 – 25 – 100 μ M	0.66 μ M	Glucose, Ascorbic acid, Citric acid, 20% Ethanol (v/v), MDMA, and Midazolam	Juice, whisky, Cachaça	[25]	LOQ: 2.18 μ M S: 0.20 μ A μ M ⁻¹
	PDAcSV	HMDE	Reduction $E_p = -0.87$ V 0.1M PB pH 6.0	0.94 – 70 nM	0.28 nM	Not studied	Natural water	[29]	S: 0.013 nA nM ⁻¹
Lorazepam 	DPV	MMWCNTs/PGE/HF	Oxidation $E_p = +0.3$ V 0.1M PB pH 6.0	0.032 – 64 μ M	0.003 μ M	Ascorbic acid, glucose, urea, and uric acid.	Water, Urine, Hair	[42]	LOQ: 0.06 μ M S: 1.7 μ A nM ⁻¹

	SWV	NiO/SWCNTs/CPE	Oxidation $E_p = \sim +0.94$ V 0.1M PB pH 7.0	0.1–280 μM	50 nM	Not studied	Drinking water	[43]	S: $0.371 \mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$
Clozapine 	ITV	eLLI	Ion transfer $E_p = \sim +0.475$ V 10mM NaCl 10mM HCl 5mM BTPPATPBCl	15 – 150 μM	1 μM	Not studied	apple juice, vodka, vodka + apple juice, wine, and beer	[45]	First report on the use of eLLI to screen BDZ in beverage samples.
Midazolam	SWV	PEI-LSG	Reduction $E_p = -1.05$ V 0.1M BRB pH 4.0	2.5 – 25 – 100 μM	0.61 μM	Glucose, Ascorbic acid, Citric acid, 20% Ethanol (v/v),	Juice, whisky, Cachaça.	[25]	LOQ: 2.01 μM S: $0.094 \mu\text{A } \mu\text{M}^{-1}$

						MDMA, and Diazepam			
	SWV	ePADs	Reduction $E_p = -0.82$ V 0.1M PBS pH 3.5	7.6 - 460.4 μ M	6.1 μ M	Citrate, lactose, Citric acid, PEG 6000	Water, Beer, liquor, vodka.	[26]	A reusable microelectrode array fabrication is demonstrated
	DPV	BDDE	Oxidation $E_p = +1.7$ V 0.1M BRB pH 4.0	4 - 25 μ M 1 - 10 μ M 1 - 15 μ M	0.46 μ M 0.43 μ M 0.33 μ M	Clonazepam Flunitrazepam, and Diazepam	Vodka, Whiskey, Red wine.	[32]	S: 0.038 μ A μ M ⁻¹ S: 0.116 μ A μ M ⁻¹ S: 0.065 μ A μ M ⁻¹
Alprazolam	PDAdCSV	HMDE	Reduction $E_p = -0.95$ V 0.1M PB pH 7.0	1.6 - 323.8 nM	0.22 nM	Humic acids, Cu ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺ lorazepam, clonazepam, and diazepam.	Water	[28]	LOQ: 1.3 nM S: 0.017 nA nM ⁻¹

<p>Ketamine</p>	CV	nanocrystal Zeo-GO E μ PAD	Oxidation $E_p = +1.5$ V 50 mM SPB, pH 7.0	0.001 – 5 μ M	1 nM	glucose, fructose, maltose, AA, hydrocortisone, gentamycine, K ⁺ , Na ⁺ , Cu ²⁺ , Ni ²⁺ , Fe ³⁺	Whiskey, Orange juice, Urine	[53]	This work report paper based microfluidic device for the detection of Ketamine.
	DPV	Wearable 3D- printed electrochemical finger (e-finger)	Oxidation $E_p \approx +1.53$ V 0.2 mol·L ⁻¹ H ₂ SO ₄	0.5 – 4 mM	0.18 mM	Buscopan, Ketamidol, Depon	whiskey, vodka, gin, beer	[37]	(i) 3D-printed wearable device for on-the-spot self-checking and onsite forensic investigation.

	Potentiometry	Carbon-SPE/PANI/ ISM(MIP)	Double junction Ag/AgCl, 10mM PB pH 4.0	1.0 μM - 10 mM	0.929 μM	Na ⁺ , K ⁺ , Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺ , Zn ²⁺ , Quetiapine	non- alcoholic beverages (juices), plasma, urine	[54]	Sensor follows IUPAC guidelines, Nernstian slope: 54.7 mV/decade LOQ: 1.0 μM
	ECL	GCE	Oxidation E _p = +1.1 V 1 mM acetate buffer, pH 4	0.21 - 8.41 μM	0.14 μM	ketamine	alcoholic beverage (Gordon's Gin & Tonic)	[52]	ECL has been used for the first time for the electroanalytical detection of Ketamine.
Morphine	DPV	SWCNTs/GCE	Oxidation E _p = +0.35 V 10 M PBS pH 7.4	0.7 - 350 μM	0.22 μM	ascorbic acid, dopamine, aspirin, acetaminophen, tetracycline, phenylalanine, valine, citric	Milk, coffee	[55]	This is the only report that studied Morphine spiked in beverage samples.

						acid, salicylic acid, niacin NaNO ₃ , glucose, fructose, xylose, ribose, galactose, Cl ⁻ , CO ₃ ²⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , Ca ²⁺ , Mg ²⁺			
GHB 	CV+ CA	PtNPs-PVA/GC	Oxidation E _p = +0.90 V 0.1M PA pH 4.0	1 - 75 mM	0.872 mM	Ethanol	lemonade, lemonade+ Vodka, Vodka, Whisky, Rum, Tequila, Gin	[69]	This is the only electroanalytical report that studied GHB spiked in alcoholic beverages.

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866 LDR- Liner detection range, LOD-Limit of detection, LOQ- Limit of quantification, S-Sensitivity, GCE-Glassy carbon electrode, EPGCE-

867 Electrochemically pretreated glassy carbon electrode, SPCE/SPE- Screen printed carbon electrode, SPGE- Screen printed graphite electrode

868 GC-Carbon sheet, CPE-Carbon Paste electrode, CoOOH-rGO: Cobalt oxyhydroxide nanoflakes/reduced graphene oxide, PEI-LSG: Laser-

869 scribing graphene/polyetherimide, ePADs- Electrochemical paper-based analytical device, CFVE- carbon fibre veil electrode, LC-DED:

870 liquid chromatography dual electrode detection, PVA-Polyvinyl alcohol, PtNPs-Platinum nanoparticles, SWCNTs-Single walled Carbon
871 nanotubes, MWCNTs- Multi walled Carbon nanotubes, NiO-Nickel Oxide, GHB- gamma-hydroxybutyric acid, GOx/GluHD-FeSPCE- glucose
872 oxidase (GOx)/ glucose hydrogel droplets (GluHD)/Iron-spark Screen printed carbon electrode (FeSPCE), AdSV/ASV- Adsorption Stripping
873 Voltammetry, DPV- Differential pulse voltammetry, HDV- Hydrodynamic voltammetry, SWV- Square Wave Voltammetry, CA-
874 Chronoamperometry, PDAcsCV - Differential pulse adsorptive cathodic stripping voltammetry, HMDE : hanging mercury drop electrode,
875 BDDE: boron-doped diamond electrode, MDMA: 3,4-Methylenedioxyamphetamine, nanocrystal Zeo-GO E μ PAD: nanocrystals of
876 zeolites (Zeo) and graphene oxide (GO) nanoflakes integrated electrochemical micro fluidic paper-based analytical device (E μ PAD),
877 MIM/GCE- molecular imprinted membrane modified glassy carbon electrode, ECL: electrochemiluminescence, PANI- polyaniline.
878 BTPPATBPCl- 1,1,1-triphenyl-N-(triphenylphosphoranylidene)phosphoraniminium tetrakis(4-chlorophenyl)borate; E_p: Electrode
879 potential against standard Ag/AgCl electrode in Sat. KCl or 3M KCl. ^aE_p: Electrode potential against carbon black reference electrode ^bE_p:
880 Electrode potential against Ag ink pseudo reference electrode.

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888 **Table 2:** Electroanalytical solutions reported for rapid detection of DRD in beverages: milestones, limitations, and future perspectives.

DRD	Existing electroanalytical probes	Methodological milestone	Key electroanalytical limitations.	Future direction
<i>Benzodiazepines</i>	Bare and modified SPCE, GCE, BDDE, and 3D printed electrodes.	The wearable e-Finger[37] and LSG-PEI[25] based multi drug sensors are a promising to provide a comprehensive electroanalytical solutions for BDZ sensing.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Electrochemical interference of coexisting species from sample matrix. 2. Surface passivation. 3. Electrode fouling. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Efficient modifiers to minimize surface passivation, electrode fouling, and chemical interference. 2. A comprehensive electrochemical profile of sensing media has to be developed.
<i>Ketamine</i>	Printed and modified carbon electrodes, GCE and ECL probes.	Paper based E μ PAD[53] and wearable e-Finger[37] are the promising tools for comprehensive	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The electroanalytical signals of KT at EμPAD are not refined to meet the standards for on-site screening of KT in beverage samples. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The fabrication methodologies and electrode modification strategies has to be improved to obtain refined electroanalytical signal for KT to improve the analytical

		detection of ketamine in beverage samples.		reliability of the future sensing solutions.
<i>New psychoactive substances</i>	Printed and modified carbon electrodes.	Flash printed carbon electrode to detect morphine[55] in milk and Lab-on-glove to screen fentanyl[56] in street samples are promising analytical tools for NPS screening.	1. Undefined toxicological and electrochemical behaviour of various NPS.	1. A comprehensive electrochemical study on the electrochemical behaviour of various NPS has to be studied documented to be used for analytical references.
<i>Gamma hydroxy butyrate</i>	Modified GCE	GC/PtNPs/PVA is the sole report of GHB[69] detection in alcoholic medium.	1. Poor electrochemical behaviour of GHB. 2. Limited resources on electrochemical behaviour of GHB in various mediums.	1. The research to explore the electrochemical behaviour of GHB at modified/ fabricated electrodes has to be amplified to maximize the sensitivity of GHB redox reactions. 2. The electrochemical profile of

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				GHB at various sensing mediums (including non-alcoholic) has to be studied.
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